

A new fully automated operational modal analysis algorithm intended for large civil structures

A C Dederichs^{1,2}, O Øiseth¹

¹ Dept. of Structural Mechanics, Norwegian University of Science and Technology

² Corresponding author: anno.c.dederichs@ntnu.no

Abstract. A new fully automated operational modal analysis (AOMA) algorithm based on the time-domain covariance-driven stochastic subspace identification (cov-SSI) system identification method is proposed. The new algorithm is intended for large civil structures, such as long-span suspension bridge for which an application example is included. It is shown that the new algorithm is capable of consistently detecting all expected structural modes of the Hardanger bridge, without requiring any prior tuning or parameter selection. The dominating three-step approach to AOMA algorithms in published literature on this topic is highlighted and used as a basis for the new algorithm; it first removes spurious poles using a Gaussian mixture model by analysing their distance to their nearest neighbour. Secondly, hierarchical clustering is used to regroup similar poles, and finally, the groups representing physical modes are selected through a similarity analysis of the size of hierarchical clusters.

1. Introduction

It is beyond any doubt that society has reached a major turning point in which sustainability is necessary in all domains. This is especially important on large-scale projects, such as those often linked to civil infrastructure like long-span road bridges, due to their size and environmental impact. Prolonging the service life of existing infrastructure generates fewer negative impacts than replacing it with a new equivalent. However, from a safety perspective, it is crucial to know about the state of the structure before deciding to prolong its service life. For this reason, there is an increasing interest in structural health monitoring (SHM) both in research and in application. An established method of structural surveillance within SHM is to extract the eigenmodes of a structure from measurements of its behaviour and analyse their evolution in time. Automatically extracting structural modes from experimental measurements has been an active field of research since the early 2010s. Since then, many attempts to automate the traditionally manual task of interpreting a stabilisation diagram have been proposed (see, amongst others, [1–9]). Few of these methods (most notably [2]) can claim to be fully automatic and require no tuning or additional inputs from a user other than the necessary parameters to perform the required operational modal analysis (OMA) to obtain a stabilisation diagram. This work aims to provide a new fully automatic operational modal analysis (AOMA) algorithm mainly for application to large civil structures such as long-span suspension bridges, based on the lessons learnt from nearly 15 years' development of mostly semi-automated operational modal analysis algorithms.

2. Theory

2.1 Automatic operational modal analysis (AOMA) algorithms

From the earliest proposals, a multi-step approach to solving the automatic modal detection problem has generally been accepted as the solution form. Most AOMA algorithms use three main steps. Before the automation steps begin, it is necessary to perform OMA of the input data over a range of model orders; a stabilisation diagram showing model order versus detected pole frequencies can be plotted to illustrate the OMA outcome. The first step in the automation procedure is to remove noise (also known as mathematical) poles from the detected poles. The second step is then to regroup similar poles and separate them from dissimilar poles. Thirdly, a selection of which groups represent physical modes, and which do not, is made, and only the groups representing physical modes are retained. Representative modal features are extracted from each group as the final product of AOMA. The automatic modal detection process mirrors the manual process of stabilisation diagram interpretation, in which an operator will firstly mentally disregard all poles which look randomly scattered throughout the stabilisation diagram. The operator will then look for the most extended and best vertical pole alignments. This step is simultaneously grouping similar poles together and disregarding the smaller groups of similar poles that do not represent physical modes. Hence, the steps in the automatic modal detection procedure can be seen as natural and are easily understandable by an inexperienced user.

These automatic operational modal analysis algorithms need to be easily understandable by their users, because, contrary to what their names imply, most algorithms are not fully automatic and require user intervention to tune the algorithm for each use case. The easier an algorithm is to understand, the easier for a user to tune the algorithm correctly. Parameters with a physical meaning are often easier to select than abstract parameters. The goal of an ideal AOMA algorithm is to be fully user-parameter free, so that it is rapidly applicable to a large range of cases. The automation level of an AOMA algorithm can be qualified based on two criteria. The first criterion is whether the algorithm requires a direct value selection, such as a pre-defined minimum number of poles in a cluster, to be considered physical, or an indirect value selection, such as a hierarchical cut-off distance derived from the data's statistical properties. The second criterion is whether any value selection decisions (direct or indirect) are taken at a primary step in the algorithm, or if they are only input into a subroutine of the algorithm. Only an algorithm which does not require any direct value selections, and where all indirect selections are made as part of subroutines, can be considered fully automatic.

In 2009, Magalhaes et al. [1] proposed an AOMA algorithm for long-span bridge applications based on the three main steps discussed. The initial removal of noise poles is done by removing all poles whose closest neighbour (in terms of frequency, damping, or mode shape) at the next inferior model order is further away than a deterministic threshold. The poles remaining after this step are grouped together using hierarchical clustering with a pre-determined cut-off distance. Lastly, the physical modes are chosen as the n largest modes. The representative features of each mode are calculated as the average value of all the poles attributed to that mode. Although this algorithm follows the framework for an AOMA algorithm, it cannot be considered fully automatic because it relies on a user to make multiple direct value choices as part of the tuning of the algorithm. In 2012, Reynders et al. [2] proposed a fully-automatic AOMA algorithm. To the authors' knowledge, it is the first AOMA algorithm to achieve full automation. The first step relies on k-means clustering to independently select which poles are potentially physical and which poles are noise. The potentially physical poles are grouped using hierarchical clustering, but the cut-off threshold is determined from the input data's statistical properties. Finally, large clusters are chosen as physical modes, with the decision of what is a large cluster and what is a small cluster being left to another k-means clustering process. The representative modal features are chosen as the median pole in each cluster in terms of damping value. In 2017, Cabboi et al. [5] proposed a new algorithm that is still based on the three steps discussed above but uses new subroutines in each step. In the first step, the noise poles are cleared by disregarding all poles above a certain deterministic

modal complexity index (MCI) threshold. The MCI is a combined measure of modal phase collinearity (MPC) and mean phase deviation (MPD). The second step uses an iterative similarity combination algorithm, which works like a guided version of hierarchical clustering. A pole is chosen starting at the lowest model order, and a new cluster is created. Iterating through all poles in increasing model order, if any pole is below a threshold distance, it is added to the cluster and the threshold distance is updated. The process is repeated until no unclustered poles remain. In the third step, all groups from step 2 are regarded as physical modes and their features are found by averaging the frequency and mode shape and selecting the median damping value of all poles in a group. In 2020, Kvåle and Øiseth [8] used a combined hierarchical and density-based algorithm (HDBSCAN) capable of performing steps two and three together. The noise poles are removed in step 1 by traditional stabilisation diagram analysis. The characteristics of each structural mode are found by averaging the features of all the poles in each group found by HDBSCAN.

Many other AOMA algorithms have also been suggested. These other algorithms are generally like the previously detailed algorithms, with newer algorithms improving upon their predecessors for specific cases. A selection of important AOMA algorithms is presented in Table 1, showing what subroutines are employed at each of the three steps and a note on their automation level.

Table 1. Overview of selected AOMA algorithms for civil structures.

Algorithm	Step 1	Step 2	Step 3	Fully automated
Magalhaes et al. 2009 [1]	Traditional stabilisation clearing	Hierarchical clustering	N-largest groups; averaged features	No
Reynders et al. 2012 [2]	k-means	Hierarchical clustering	k-means; selection of rep. poles	Yes
Zhang et al. 2014 [3]	Energy similarity analysis	Hierarchical clustering	Large groups; (averaged features)	No
Cardoso et al. 2017 [4]	Thresholds on damping and MPC	Multiple hierarchical clustering analyses	N largest groups; averaged features	No
Caboi et al. 2017 [5]	Thresholds on mode shape complexity	Iterative similarity clustering	All groups; averaged or median features	No
Neu et al. 2017 [6]	k-means	Hierarchical clustering	Large groups; averages features	No
Yang et al. 2019 [7]	Fuzzy-c-means	Iterative similarity clustering	Large groups; selection of rep. poles.	No
Kvåle and Øiseth 2020 [8]	Traditional stabilisation clearing	HDBSCAN	HDBSCAN (combined with step 2); averaged features	No
Tronci et al. 2022 [9]	Generalised similarity analysis	Blind k-means or DBSCAN	(Combined with step 2); averaged features	No

2.2 Gaussian Mixture Models

A Gaussian mixture model is an unsupervised machine learning method part of the clustering family. It can be used to group elements with similarities and separate elements with dissimilarities. A K-component Gaussian mixture assumes that the data is sampled following $K \in \mathbb{N}$ multivariate normal distributions, with means $\boldsymbol{\mu}_k$, covariances Σ_k , and a mixing weight of π_k , where $k \in \{1, \dots, K\}$ and $\sum_{k=1}^K \pi_k = 1$.

The maximum likelihood of the mixing model describes the optimal clustering solution and is determined by maximising the joint probability of all $N \in \mathbb{N}$ observations $\mathbf{x}_n \in X = \{\mathbf{x}_1, \dots, \mathbf{x}_N\}$. The log-maximum likelihood also gives the optimal solution:

$$\ln p(X) = \sum_{n=1}^N \ln \sum_{k=1}^K \pi_k \mathcal{N}(\mathbf{x}_n | \boldsymbol{\mu}_k, \Sigma_k) \quad (1)$$

The Expectation-Maximisation algorithm is an iterative method to approximate the maximisation problem of Equation 1, shown to always tend towards a local maximum. The two-step iterative procedure assumes an initial guess for all $\boldsymbol{\mu}_k$, Σ_k , and π_k . In the first step, an expectation value $\gamma(z_{nk})$ of observation n belonging to cluster k is estimated, based on the latest knowledge of the cluster parameters:

$$\gamma(z_{nk}) = \frac{\pi_k \mathcal{N}(\mathbf{x}_n | \boldsymbol{\mu}_k, \Sigma_k)}{\sum_{i=1}^K \pi_i \mathcal{N}(\mathbf{x}_n | \boldsymbol{\mu}_i, \Sigma_i)} \quad (2)$$

In the second step (the maximisation step), new estimates of the cluster features are made:

$$\pi_k^* = \frac{\sum_{n=1}^N \gamma(z_{nk})}{N} \quad (3)$$

$$\boldsymbol{\mu}_k^* = \frac{\sum_{n=1}^N \gamma(z_{nk}) \mathbf{x}_n}{\sum_{n=1}^N \gamma(z_{nk})} \quad (4)$$

$$\Sigma_k^* = \frac{\sum_{n=1}^N \gamma(z_{nk}) (\mathbf{x}_n - \boldsymbol{\mu}_k)(\mathbf{x}_n - \boldsymbol{\mu}_k)^T}{\sum_{n=1}^N \gamma(z_{nk})} \quad (5)$$

The iterations continue until there is no more increase in the log-maximum likelihood of Equation 1, at which point the optimal solution has been reached.

3. Proposed algorithm

The new AOMA algorithm proposed in this work is presented in the following section. The algorithm takes inspiration from the existing AOMA algorithms in terms of methods employed and form followed. The strengths and weaknesses of existing AOMA algorithms have been previously mapped through a thorough performance review. The new algorithm combines these highlighted strengths and maintains a similar functional form. An operator with knowledge of the functionality of earlier AOMA algorithms should find this new algorithm familiar and easy to understand and implement. The algorithm is primarily designed to work using the output from the covariance-driven stochastic subspace identification (cov-SSI) OMA of the recorded vibration data from a structure, but other system identification methods remain applicable. The necessary input variables are the detected poles representing the eigenvalues of the vibration system, extracted for a range of model orders used at the OMA step.

3.1 Removal of mathematical poles

Once all the poles from the OMA step are available, two steps of mathematical pole removal are performed, firstly based on fixed, physical thresholds ('hard' criteria), and secondly based on the variations between the poles ('soft' criteria).

3.1.1 *'Hard' criteria.* All poles with one of the three following characteristics are flagged as mathematical and removed from all future processes:

- Negative damping value,
- The pole is real,
- The pole has no complex conjugate “twin” pole.

Furthermore, if the operational modal analysis has been performed on data sampled at a high sampling rate to reduce the number of mathematical poles in the frequency range of interest, all poles above the frequency range of interest can be disregarded at this step. To increase the performance of the algorithm, it is also possible, at this step, to exclude any poles with unrealistically high damping (for example above the 20% to 30% range). Both these considerations are optional, and one can proceed without performing them, if a fully user-parameter free algorithm is necessary.

3.1.2 *'Soft' criteria.* Each pole is given a relative distance in frequency, modal phase collinearity (MPC), and mode shape to its nearest neighbour at the next inferior modal order. If a relative distance is small, it is assumed that the pole is more likely to be a real physical manifestation than if a relative distance is large, because physical poles should appear with similar properties at each model order, whereas mathematical poles should not. The distance in frequency and MPC are calculated using Equation 6 and the difference in mode shape using the inverse modal assurance criterion (MAC) (Equation 7).

$$dx_{i,j} = \frac{|x_i - x_j|}{\max(|x_i|, |x_j|)} \quad (6)$$

x_i and x_j are either frequency values or MPC values, depending on whether the relative difference is calculated in frequency or in MPC.

$$dMAC_{i,j} = 1 - \frac{|\phi_i^T \phi_j^*|^2}{(\phi_i^T \phi_i^*)(\phi_j^T \phi_j^*)} \quad (7)$$

The relative differences are input into a 2-component Gaussian Mixture Model (GMM) to identify which poles are most likely to be physical and which are most likely to be mathematical. The GMM replaces k-means (or fuzzy-c-means) clustering. It has the advantage of dealing with non-equal variances in the data dimensions. It is a fuzzy classifier as each data point is given a certain probability of belonging to each cluster. The resulting cluster whose norm of its mean value vector is closest to zero is the stable cluster, and the poles in the unstable cluster are disregarded in further analyses.

3.2 Grouping of similar poles

The remaining poles are combined into groups of similar characteristics using hierarchical clustering. The groups are supposed to represent the physical modes of the structure. Multiple realisations of the same physical mode across different model orders are to be grouped together and separated from the realisations of different physical modes. The hierarchical clustering procedure uses single linkage, due to its computational efficiency and because it is not worse than other linkage methods in experimental comparisons [10]. The pair-wise distance matrix between all poles is calculated as follows:

$$d_{i,j} = df_{i,j} + 1 - MAC_{i,j} \quad (8)$$

When choosing which model orders to include in the OMA, one makes an implicit decision on the number of modes present in the data. The expected number of modes can be seen as the average model

order. Therefore, the hierarchical clustering is set to create the same number of clusters as the average model order. This bypasses the need to set a cut-off value, which is notoriously difficult to do.

Each resulting hierarchical cluster is analysed to retain only one single pole per model order. If there are multiple poles per model order, only the pole with the lowest average distance (as defined in Equation 8) to all the other poles in the cluster is kept.

As the average model order, and the number of hierarchical clusters, should be larger than the actual number of modes present in the data, similar poles are combined, and the remaining noise poles are attributed their own cluster. One physical mode can be split into multiple hierarchical clusters. Recombining similar hierarchical clusters is therefore necessary to avoid these duplicate detections. Based on the outcome of the initial GMM clustering (Section 3.1.2), it is possible to define thresholds for the similarity of modal features. The thresholds for similarity in frequency, MPC, and mode shape are defined as the averages between the centres of both Gaussian mixtures for each feature respectively, weighted by the weight of each mixture:

$$dx_{sim} = \pi_0\mu_{x,0} + \pi_1\mu_{x,1} \quad (9)$$

where x is either difference in frequency, in MPC or in MAC. If the distances between the average features of two hierarchical clusters are below all three thresholds, the two clusters are considered similar and merged into one cluster.

3.3 Selection of stable groups

Even after combining similar hierarchical clusters, there will remain more hierarchical clusters than measurable physical modes. This is because the initial definition of the number of clusters is bound to be larger than the actual number modes and the non-physical hierarchical clusters contain the noise poles remaining after the clearing step. Two types of hierarchical clusters are thus present in the analysis. Firstly, clusters of physical poles which are characterised by having many elements and, secondly, clusters of mathematical poles which tend to have a single or few elements.

This algorithm proposes an automatic procedure to separate the two types of hierarchical clusters, based on two features, which are:

- The number of elements in the cluster (cluster size) n_i ,
- The number of clusters of a similar size (near neighbours count) $s_{nn,i}$.

The first feature does not require an explanation. The second feature is obtained by counting the number of other clusters with a size within a tolerance range of the target cluster size. The aim of this step is to highlight the size proximity of the multitude of small noise clusters by giving them a high score based on the number of clusters of similar size (near neighbours count), to help differentiate them from the physical clusters, which tend to have a much more scattered cluster size distribution (because they start appearing at different model orders in the OMA, and therefore have a lower near neighbour count). The tolerance range needs to be chosen large enough to contain all (or at least most) of the noise clusters, but as small as possible, so that physical clusters are not within the neighbourhood of noise clusters. The tolerance range is found by exploiting the bimodal distribution which appears in the average distance (in terms of cluster size) from one cluster to all others. Keeping the initial assumption that there are more non-physical clusters than physical clusters, the mean of the first mode of the distribution represents the average distance from one non-physical cluster to another. The tolerance range is thus defined. Two clusters with an absolute difference in size inferior to half the tolerance range are considered near neighbours. The statistical properties of the two modes of a bimodal distribution can be efficiently estimated by fitting a 2-component Gaussian mixture model to the distribution.

Once the two features are determined for each hierarchical cluster, a new two-component Gaussian Mixture Model can be fitted to the two features to determine which groups are physical modes and which are noise. The starting points for the GMM procedure are chosen as:

$$\mathbf{m}_0^{(0)} = [0 \quad \max(\mathbf{s}_{nn})], \quad \mathbf{m}_1^{(0)} = [\max(\mathbf{n}) \quad 0] \quad (10)$$

where $\mathbf{m}_0^{(0)}$ and $\mathbf{m}_1^{(0)}$ are the initial starting points for components 0 and 1, \mathbf{s}_{nn} and \mathbf{n} are the respective feature vectors containing the $s_{nn,i}$ and n_i . After clustering, the mixture with the largest mean value for the cluster size is chosen as the physical one, and all the hierarchical clusters attributed to this mixture correspond to the detected modes. The modal features of a detected mode are chosen as the mean values of the all the poles within a physical hierarchical cluster.

4. Application examples

This work presents two application examples: a numerically generated shear frame, and experimental measurements from the Hardanger suspension bridge in South-Western Norway. The numerical setup is a nine-storey shear frame excited by white noise. The vibration acceleration data is simulated in the time-domain for each storey and random, normally distributed measurement noise with the same variance as the vibrations is added to the signals. The sample rate is taken as 200 Hz, which is roughly 100 times the lowest mode frequency and seven times the highest mode frequency. Six minutes of vibration data are used as an input into the cov-SSI using $i = 200$ block-rows and even model orders ranging from 8 to 80.

Figure 1 illustrates the proposed algorithm's process, showing the intermediate states after each main step is performed. Graph a) shows the output of the cov-SSI procedure, where nice vertical alignments of poles are visible for all nine structural modes. However, only the structural mode with the lowest natural frequency clearly stands out, all the other modes either have a duplication of their detection (modes 2-4) or are beleaguered with noise poles (modes 5-9). After step 1 of the algorithm, which removes as many noise poles as possible, the vertical alignments of possibly physical poles (Graph b)) becomes a lot more visible. All modes are clearly visible, modes 5-9 are still surrounded by a small amount of noise poles, and mode 3 still has a second alignment right next to it. Graph c) shows the state of clustering after step 2, once hierarchical clustering and recombination of the highly similar modes is complete. The poles representing structural modes are clustered into a single cluster per mode, each with many poles, whereas the remaining noise poles mostly have been clustered into individual groups, or into small groups. After the final step, as seen in Graph d), when the many smaller clusters are removed, only clusters representing the physical modes of the structure are left. All the structural modes are identified. Modes 5 and 6 are both contain some noise poles which do not align perfectly with the actual physical poles. It is not a big problem that these noise poles are included in physical modes, firstly because there only are a few misclassifications, and secondly, because these misclassifications happen due to the high similarity between the noise poles and the physical mode.

The second application example uses the experimental vibration measurements from the Hardanger suspension bridge in Norway. The bridge is a 1300 m main span suspension bridge featuring a very narrow deck, composed of only two traffic lanes and a pedestrian and cycle path, resulting in high flexibility. The behaviour of the bridge deck has been monitored using 20 triaxial accelerometers since 2013. These data recordings are openly available [11]. The bridge has previously been extensively studied, both numerically [12,13] and experimentally [10,14], leading to a good understanding of which structural modes exist and can be detected. Table 2 presents the modes which are expected to be detected from the experimental measurements of the Hardanger bridge. The expected frequencies are plotted as red vertical lines in Figure 2d).

Figure 1. Proposed AOMA algorithm step-by-step process. Shear frame simulated data.

Table 2. Hardanger bridge known structural modes [10,12–14].

Mode number	Numerical Frequency [Hz]	Mode shape description	Experimental detection [ref] [Hz]	Tolerance range [Hz]
1	0.05	Horizontal	0.052	[0.049, 0.055]
2	0.098	Horizontal	0.105	[0.099, 0.107]
3	0.11	Vertical	0.119	[0.111, 0.124]
4	0.14	Vertical	0.142	[0.139, 0.145]
5	0.169	Horizontal	0.183	[0.177, 0.186]
6	0.197	Vertical	0.206	[0.201, 0.209[
7	0.21	Vertical	0.212	[0.209, 0.216]
8	0.233	Horizontal + cables, lateral	0.230	[0.227, 0.234]
9	0.272	Vertical	0.276	[0.273, 0.279]
10	0.293	Horizontal	0.318	[0.308, 0.323]
11	0.33	Vertical	0.333	[0.328, 0.338]
12	0.36	Torsional	0.374	[0.362, 0.376]
13	0.394	Vertical	0.401	[0.396, 0.406]
14	0.406	Horizontal + cables, lateral	0.418	[0.412, 0.420]

The cov-SSI modal analysis is performed on 10 minutes of data downsampled to 20 Hz, using $i = 200$ block-rows, and even model orders ranging from 20 to 200. Figure 2 shows the proposed AOMA algorithm's step-by-step process on a dataset from the Hardanger suspension bridge. Graph a) shows all the poles identified by cov-SSI. Vertical alignments are visible throughout the frequency range, but many noise poles are also present making the stabilisation diagram hard to interpret. Step 1 (Graph b)) is effective at removing many noise poles, leading to a much clearer stabilisation diagram. Step 2 (Graph c)) creates many combined hierarchical clusters, but it is visible that some clusters contain many poles from the same vertical alignment and many other clusters contain only few noise poles. Step 3 (Graph d)) removes all the smaller noise clusters, leaving only the structural modes to be detected. The algorithm detects all 14 expected modes, without making any false detections.

Figure 2. Proposed AOMA algorithm step-by-step process. Hardanger bridge experimental data.

Figure 3 shows the detected modal frequencies from 50 datasets from the Hardanger bridge using the proposed AOMA algorithm. The grey lines mark the expected frequencies of each mode; due to different excitation conditions, the modal frequencies are expected to vary slightly. The algorithm can consistently detect most structural modes, while committing very few false detections. The expected structural mode with a 0.23 Hz frequency is notoriously difficult to detect, because most of the movement is concentrated in the cables, which are not instrumented. The ten modal detections around the 0.23 Hz line are detections of this mode, which is also subject to large variations in frequency depending on the excitation conditions. The proposed algorithm has no difficulty in detecting closely spaced modes, as can be seen with modes 6 and 7, which are both detected in 49 of the 50 datasets. Overall, the proposed algorithm performs well on data which is notoriously noisy and difficult to interpret.

Figure 3. Detected mode frequencies using the proposed AOMA algorithm for 50 datasets from the Hardanger bridge. The grey lines mark the expected modal frequencies.

5. Conclusion

A new fully automatic operational modal analysis (AOMA) algorithm is proposed, based on lessons learnt from previous AOMA algorithms. It is based on the well-established three main steps procedure developed since the early 2010s. An initial clearing of noise poles from the stabilisation diagram resulting from the cov-SSI analysis is performed using a 2-component Gaussian mixture model. The remaining poles are clustered into groups based on similarity using hierarchical clustering. Finally, noise

groups and groups representing physical modes are separated using a second 2-component Gaussian mixture model based on size similarity of the groups. The proposed algorithm is fully automatic requiring no additional inputs from a user other than those required for the cov-SSI analysis. The algorithm is shown to perform well on a numerically generated shear frame and on experimental data from the Hardanger bridge, where the structural modes are consistently detected across many different data recordings.

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